

irrigated separately were established.

IR36 and IR58 and four rates of carbofuran (Furadan 3G) were used in a randomized complete block design with five replications.

Seedling nurseries were established in the field without nematicide treatment of the seedbeds. Cultivars were transplanted at a 20- × 20-cm spacing. Plots were weeded two times a week to maximum tillering. No fertilizer was used.

Carbofuran was applied in two equal splits 3 d before and 30 d after transplanting. The first application was incorporated, the second was placed at the soil surface in standing water. The field was flooded with 5-10 cm water from transplanting to harvest.

Nematode numbers in roots and soil were estimated at maximum tillering, booting, flowering, and harvest. The central 3-m² area in each plot was reserved for evaluating yield.

All the carbofuran treatments significantly reduced *Hirschmanniella* spp. population (see table). Populations at maximum tillering and booting in plots treated with 4 and 8 kg ai carbofuran/ha were significantly lower than those in plots treated with 2 kg ai/ha.

Carbofuran-treated plots also produced significantly higher yields. The yield increase was correlated with number of nematodes and with rate of carbofuran applied (see figure).

Because nematode densities in plots treated with 4 and 8 kg ai/ha did not differ significantly, differences in yield cannot be totally attributed to the reduction in nematodes.

In previous greenhouse experiments conducted in the absence of parasites, carbofuran appeared to stimulate rice growth. It is also an insecticide. Other nematicide (dibromochloropane and ethylene dibromide) also are suspected to be plant growth stimulators.

Hirschmanniella spp. may cause yield losses in irrigated rice. However, we are unable to estimate the part of the yield increase attributable to a nematicide treatment.

Despite the tremendous increases in rice yield reported after control of *H.*

Influence of carbofuran treatments on yield of rice cultivars IR36 and IR58 and population densities of *Hirschmanniella* spp. at different growth stages.^a

Carbofuran (kg ai/ha)	Yield (g/3 m ²)		Population densities of <i>Hirschmanniella</i> spp./liter soil + 3 g roots							
	Yield		Maximum tillering		Booting		Flowering		Maturity	
	IR36	IR58	IR36	IR58	IR36	IR58	IR36	IR58	IR36	IR58
0	539 a	481 a	152 a	210 a	295 a	337 a	438 a	584 a	1160 a	683 a
2	1120 b	861 b	28 b	35 b	57 b	50 b	103 b	100 b	234 b	203 b
4	1461 c	1278 c	9 c	8 c	21 c	21 c	75 b	64 b	111 c	150 b
8	2038 d	1546 d	7 c	8 c	7 c	6 d	54 b	62 b	65 c	102 b

^aAv of 5 replications. In a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

a) Correlation between number of *Hirschmanniella* spp. per liter soil plus 3 g of roots and yield of rice cultivar IR58. b) Correlation between rate of carbofuran and yield of rice cultivar IR58.

mucronata and *H. oryzae* by nematicides, the actual reductions in irrigated

rice yields caused by rice root nematodes are still controversial. □

Chemical control of crabs in ricefields

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Crabs (*Paratelpusa hydroromus*, Herbst) dig burrows in the bunds of ricefields, allowing water to flow from one field to another. Applied fertilizers or pesticides may get diluted and upper fields dry out while water

stagnates in lower fields.

We tested the efficacy of commonly available insecticides (see table) offered as bait or directly applied during 1984 wet season.

All crab burrows on the bunds of a ricefield at DRR experimental farm were closed with mud. The next day, new burrows were counted.

Bait was prepared by diluting 200 g of each insecticide in 50 ml of water, then mixing the solution into 1 kg cooked rice. A 50-g bait was placed inside each burrow. For direct application, about 5 g of the test granular insecticide was placed in each burrow, along with 200-300 ml of water to dissolve the granules (1.5 g of celphos tablet was inserted in a moisturized burrow).

All burrows were plugged with mud and left for 24 h. Counts were taken of open burrows. Burrows not opened were considered "dead."

To verify crab mortality, 50 randomly selected "dead" burrows were dug out: crab mortality was 100%.

Celphos and phorate (81.1 and 80.3% crab mortality) were most effective in direct treatment. Fenthion was most effective (72.4% mortality) as bait. Celphos is already in use to control rats. Phorate granules are also effective in controlling other rice pests, such as stem borer. □

Control of rice rodent *Thryonomys swinderianus* in Sierra Leone

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The hystricomorph or cutting-grass rodent *T. swinderianus* Temminck is a notorious pest in rice-based cropping systems of West Africa. Chemical control measures are undesirable because the rodents are a traditional meat source in rural areas. Nonchemical control is necessary.

We monitored rodent drives (see figure) to determine the pest's reproductive cycle in the field and to identify vulnerable stages for crop protection measures.

Drives in three chiefdoms (Kholifa Mabang, Malal, and Yoni) in the Tonkolili District, Northern Province, Sierra Leone, are conducted by a team of 7 trackers, 15 chainmen (netmen), and 5 noisemakers. They use four tracker dogs and up to 18 twine nets of different lengths. Each drive lasts 8-10 h in a succession of selected plots with natural vegetation, mainly wild grasses. The noisemakers and dogs startle and scare the nocturnal rodents toward encircling nets, where they are

caught and killed.

In 27 drives Jul 1988 to Jan 1989, 301 *T. swinderianus* were killed; approximately half were females. Adults weighed 3-8 kg and were 0.6-0.85 m long.

The pest appears to breed once a year. All females caught between Jul and Oct 1988 were pregnant, with three to six fetuses each. The gestation period coincided with vegetative growth of upland rice, during which most damage to rice (patches of cut tillers) is reported, primarily at booting. Of 404 fetuses dissected, those within a month's collection were of similar size. That implies a synchronized Jun-Jul estrus cycle.

Parturition was also synchronized, early in the dry season which is from late Oct to early Dec. Catches in those months were lower than in the rainy season.

Although these drives are primarily for catching *T. swinderianus* for human consumption, targeting them at the gestation period would have greater effects on population control. This would also be the best time for well-coordinated drives. However, catch per drive is also determined by rodent abundance and behavior, cover vegetation, and the general motivation and discipline of the hunters. □

Effect of pesticides on ricefield crabs. DRR, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad, India, 1984 wet season.

Treatment	Burrows treated (no.)	Burrows found opened after 24 h of treatment (no.)	Unopened burrows (%)
<i>With bait</i>			
Carbofuran	52	24	53.8
Quinalphos	92	55	40.3
Phorate	28	13	63.9
Fenthion	58	16	72.4
Control	47	41	12.8
<i>Without bait</i>			
Carbofuran	80	42	47.5
Quinalphos	87	50	37.5
Phorate	61	12	80.3
Fenthion	42	20	52.4
Celphos	90	17	81.1
Control	63	59	6.4

Chainmen positioning nets around a grassy plot containing *T. swinderianus* rodents in Sierra Leone.